

Arbitrage using Soya Bean and Soya meal futures contract
Evidence from Dalian Commodity Exchange, China

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ORIGINAL

Abstract - We investigate the price discovery process among the futures prices of soybean and soya meal contracts in the Dalian Commodity Exchange. Granger Causality Test, Co-integration Test and Error Correction Model (ECM) will be used to measure soybean, and soybean meal future price. If the two commodities' future price have strong relationship in short or long term, the portfolio of cross-species arbitrage was produced through Co-integration Relationship. Other factors such as liquidity, transaction costs, and other market restrictions may produce an empirical lead-lag relationship between price changes in the two markets. Moreover, all the markets do not trade simultaneously for many assets and commodities. We select the main contract from November 15th, 2005 to March 28th, 2012, which contain 1547 data respectively. All the data can be divided into two groups, one is from November 15th, 2005 to December 31th, 2010, which contain 1247 data respectively; the other is from January 4th, 2011 to March 28th. Our test results suggest a strong bi-directional causality in futures prices. We also find that the soybean contract bears the burden of convergence between soybean and soymeal prices.

Keywords - Price discovery; Granger Causality; Volatility; Spillover; Commodity markets; soya bean; soya meals.

I. INTRODUCTION

Commodity prices have undergone strong fluctuations as a consequence of economic, political and financial issues affecting the particular and global market. Futures markets have been the main contributor to price stability and food production for the world in the last 50 years. China in 1960 face famine and a recent CCTV documentary reported that 50 million people were affected by food shortages in the Yangtze river delta at that time.

Price discovery and risk transfer are considered to be two major contributions of futures market (Garbade and Silber, 1983). Price discovery refers to the use of future prices for pricing cash market transactions. This implies that futures price serves as market's expectations of subsequent spot price. Understanding the influence of one market on the other and the role of each market segment in price discovery is the central question in market microstructure design and is very important to academia and regulators.

Unfortunately Dalian Commodity Exchange is not a perfect market so some insiders may have privileged information and therefore could make arbitrage profits. In efficient markets, new information is impounded simultaneously into cash and futures markets (Zhong et al. 2004). In other words, financial market pricing theory states

that market efficiency is a function of how fast and how much information is reflected in prices. The rate at which prices exhibit market information is the rate at which this information is disseminated to market participants (Zapata et al. 2005).

In this paper we investigate the soya bean and soya meal market to study the arbitrage opportunity. Other factors such as liquidity, transaction costs, and other market restrictions may produce an empirical lead-lag relationship between price changes in the two markets. Moreover, all the markets do not trade simultaneously for many assets and commodities

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature on price discovery is extensive, most recent studies of price discovery have used the Garbade-Silber framework along with co-integration and error correction models to determine the relationship between futures and cash prices. Garbade and Silber (1983) developed a model of simultaneous price dynamics in which changes in futures and spot prices on t are a function of the basis on $t-1$.

They used the model to examine the characteristics of daily spot and futures prices for four storable agricultural commodities (wheat, corn, oats and orange juice). For wheat, corn and orange juice, they found that futures markets dominate cash markets. In contrast, they found that the pricing is more evenly divided between cash and futures markets which led them to hypothesize that market size and liquidity might affect the price discovery role of futures markets.

Following Garbade and Silber, Oellermann et al. (1989) and Schroeder and Goodwin (1991) studied the price discovery mechanism for livestock in the periods 1979-1986 and 1975-1989, respectively. Both studies tested the extent of short-run price discovery, and found that information tends to be discovered first in futures markets and then transferred to cash markets.

Both studies also adopted other procedures to verify the ir results in the long run. Oellerman et al. tested Granger-causality for the once-differenced prices and found that lagged changes in futures prices are statistically significant in explaining current changes in cash prices, but that lagged cash prices had little effect on futures prices.

Schroeder and Goodwin used co-integration procedures to verify that daily cash and futures prices for live hogs didn't share a long-run relationship. They found a short-run relationship between cash and futures prices based on Garbade-Silber model, but failed to find a long-run relationship using either Granger-causality or co-integration procedures.

A slightly different approach was adopted by Koontz et al. (1990) to study price discovery in the livestock market. Using weekly U.S. cash and futures prices from 1973 through 1984, they investigated the spatial nature of the price discovery process. They adopted the procedure proposed by Geweke (1982) to generate causality tests and measures of interaction between major cash markets, and between cash and futures markets. In general, their findings suggested that there was a high degree of interaction between cash and futures prices.

A. Studies in China

Compared to CBOT or LME, the future market in China was less studied. On Oct. 12, 1990, the establishment of the China Zhengzhou Grain Wholesale Market introduced the futures trading for the first time in the China. With the development of the future market, plenty of institutions or researchers begin to focus on it. The initial research emphasizes on Legislative issue. For example, Yao (1998) present a detailed structural analysis of the relationship between the commodities future market and governmental legislative or regulatory attempts. In addition, the development and the trait of cotton trading in the CZCE was researched by Williams, et al (1998) and they concluded the basic condition for arbitrage existed in the CZCE through the analysis of price spread between different contracts in the same year. Furthermore, the relationship between CBOT and DEC was considered by Durham and Si (1999). Later, they concluded that the soybean future price in CBOT can affect the soybean future price in DEC through one price model analysis, but one single model cannot fit the relationship between two commodities.

Engle and Grange (1987) develop the co-integration theory, which provide a new technique to analyze jointly economic variables. As a large number of economic issues have been reanalyzed using co-integration analysis, new findings and insights appears to the public. The efficiency for the UK agricultural commodities was re-investigated by Aulton, Ennew and Rayner (1997) using co-integration.

Moreover, David Yanky (2004) research on the Chinese metal future price in SHFE through using Box-Jenkin's ARIMA single process, random walk and VAR. Finally, he summarized that there is co-integration among relevant variable and vector process perform better than single series in the presence of co-integration. Following Engle and Grange develop the statistical procedures to test co-integration with maximum likelihood. These procedures allows for possible interactions to determine the spot price and future price, which was based on a VAR (Kouadio, 2007).

Zheng, Xu, Foster & Wang (2012) show that the Chinese non-GMO soybean futures market, based on data from the period 2003 to 2010, is efficient. Also, futures prices respond effectively to exogenous price shocks and that cash prices

move following these futures prices. These results provide insight into risk management strategies for global industry participants, including soybean producers, distributors and traders, government policy planners and international investors.

The studies of price discovery and volatility spillovers in Chinese spot-futures markets are very important to both the government and the producers/marketers in China. From the government policy point of view, knowing the relationships between futures and spot clearly means a better alternative to market interventions such as imposing price stabilization policies. For processors/marketers, it provides a reliable forecast of spot prices in the future to allow them to effectively manage their risks in the production or marketing process. It is also the interest of international market participants from countries like USA, UK etc, who are the major grain exporters to China. Thus this study can provide international exporters/importers of commodities with some knowledge of the conditions in Chinese commodity futures and spot markets.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Granger Causality Test

When we want to determine that past values of one series X_t are useful for forecasting future values of another series Y_t , the best method is Granger Causality Test (Granger, 1969). The Granger Causality Test is the T-statistic or F-statistic testing the hypothesis that the coefficients on all the value of one of the variables are zero (Wikipedian.d.). The null hypothesis states that these regressors have no predictive content for dependent variables beyond that contained in the other regressors, and the test of this null hypothesis is called the Granger Causality Test.

Assume: Y represents soybean meal

X represents soybean

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \beta_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \beta_p Y_{t-p} + \delta_1 X_1 + \delta_2 X_2 + \dots + \delta_p X_{t-p}. \quad (1)$$

$$X_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{t-1} + \beta_2 X_{t-2} + \dots + \beta_p X_{t-p} + \delta_1 Y_1 + \delta_2 Y_2 + \dots + \delta_p Y_{t-p}. \quad (2)$$

Under the null hypothesis, any lags of X that we add into the equation should have zero coefficients. If only X_{t-1} was added, the simple t test can be done on X_{t-1} . If two lags of X was added, then an F test for joint significance of X_{t-1} and

X_{t-2} should be done. (If the data appears heteroskedasticity, a robust form of the test should be used.) Hence, the null hypothesis that X does not Granger-cause Y is accepted if and only if no lagged values of X are retained in the regression (Arlen 2008).

TABLE I. GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST FOR SOYBEAN AND SOYBEAN MEAL FUTURE PRICE

Null Hypothesis	First Lag		Second Lag		Third Lag	
	F-Statistic	Probability	F-Statistic	Probability	F-Statistic	Probability
Y does not Granger Cause X	0.01950	0.88896	0.12159	0.88552	0.06304	0.97932
X does not Granger Cause Y	5.20300	0.02272	5.64504	0.00363	4.32025	0.00486

The table illustrates that the X does Granger Cause Y is three situation-first, second and third lag, and Y cannot Granger Causes X. Hence, the soybean future price (X) should be the explanatory variable, whereas soybean meal future price (Y) should be the response variable.

B. Order of Integration

If we want to make sure the order of integration the trend is smooth not stochastic, the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) can be used to test whether $\Delta^d Y_t$ has an autoregressive root that equals 1 has. Similarities, the ADF test on X are operated and the outcomes are shown in the table below:

TABLE II.

	Zero Difference	First Difference	Probability		
	T-Statistic	T-Statistic	10%	5%	1%
Y	-1.76	-37.92	-2.57	-2.86	-3.43
X	-1.43	-38.4			

Consequently, both Y_t and X_t appears random walk, but Y_t and X_t are integrated if order one-I (1).

C. Co-integration

Co-integration means that two or more series that have a common stochastic trend. Assume both X_t and Y_t are I (1), if $Y_t - \theta X_t$ have a stationary trend I(0), X_t and Y_t are co-integrated (Wikipedian.d.). Engle-Granger Augmented Dickey-Fuller (EG-ADF) test can be conducted to test co-integration (Engle and Granger, 1987). The Procedure includes two steps:

Step 1: When θ (co-integration coefficient) is unknown, it should be estimated prior to testing for a unit root in the error correction term. This preliminary step makes it necessary to use different critical values for subsequent unit root test. In particular, the co-integration coefficient is estimated by OLS:

$$Y_t = 614.77 + 0.61X_t + u_t \tag{3}$$

Step 2: a Dickey-Fuller t-test was needed to test for a unit root in the residual u_t from this regression. If Y_t and X_t are co-integrated, the error term in (8) is I (0). If not, u_t will be I (1). Thereby, one can test for the presence of a co-integrating relationship by testing for a unit root in the OLS residuals u_t from (8). It seems that this can be done by using the augmented Dickey-Fuller. The regression should be run like this:

$$\Delta u_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 u_{t-1} + e_t \tag{4}$$

There is, however, an additional complication in testing for unit roots in OLS residuals rather than in ordinary time series. Because the OLS estimator 'chooses' the residuals in the co-integrating regression to have as small a sample variance as possible, even if the variables are not co-integrated, the OLS estimator will make the residuals 'look' as stationary as possible. Thus, using standard DF or ADF tests, we may reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity too often. As a result, the appropriate critical values are more negative than those for standard Dickey-Fuller and are presented in table (3).

TABLE III.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test on U

Null Hypothesis: U has a unit root		
Exogenous: Constant		
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic based on SIC, MAXLAG=22)		
	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-3.801891	0.0030
Test critical values:		
1% level	-3.435385	
5% level	-2.863651	
10% level	-2.567944	

Table (3) shows the t-statistic is 3.8, which lies in the 1% rejected region, so u_t is stationary. Hence, Y_t and X_t are said to be co-integrated. The figure (2) demonstrates the actual value, fitted value and residual value for soybean meal future price.

Figure (2)

D. Error Correction Model

As it is discussed above, the stochastic trend in an I (1) variable Y_t can be eliminated by computing its first difference- ΔY ; the problems created by stochastic trends were then avoided by using ΔY instead of Y_t in time series regressions. Y_t and X_t are co-integrated, however, another way to eliminate the trend is to compute $Y_t - \theta X_t$ (called error correction term),

where θ is chosen to eliminate the common trend from the difference. Because the term $Y_t - \theta X_t$ is stationary, it can be used in regression analysis. In fact, the first differences of Y_t and X_t can be modeled using a VAR, augmented by including $Y_{t-1} - \theta X_{t-1}$ as an additional regressor. Moreover, the error correction term has no moving average part and the systematic dynamics is kept as simple as possible.

In addition, as the co-integrating regression model can only reflect the long-run property between X and Y, the short-run relationship cannot be found. Clearly, a good time series modeling should describe both short-run dynamics and the long-run equilibrium simultaneously. Y_t and X_t are both I (1) but have a long run relationship, there must be some force that pulls the equilibrium error back towards zero. The Error Correction Model (ECM) does exactly this: it describes how Y_t and X_t behaves in the short run consistent with a long run co-integrating relationship.

Dependent Variable: D(Y)				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 03/29/12 Time: 20:33				
Sample (adjusted): 3 1247				
Included observations: 1245 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.584578	0.954461	0.612469	0.5403
D(X)	0.588023	0.016013	36.72214	0.0000
ECM(-1)	-0.022652	0.005963	-3.798633	0.0002
R-squared	0.523595	Mean dependent var	0.892369	
Adjusted R-squared	0.522827	S.D. dependent var	48.19587	
S.E. of regression	33.29259	Akaike info criterion	9.850954	
Sum squared resid	1376629.	Schwarz criterion	9.863307	
Log likelihood	-6129.219	F-statistic	682.5116	
Durbin-Watson stat	2.001444	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000	

The Error Correction Model for soybean and soybean meal future price can be set:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \alpha_1 \Delta Y_{t-1} + \alpha_2 \Delta Y_{t-2} + \dots + \alpha_p \Delta Y_{t-p} + \beta_1 \Delta X_{t-1} + \beta_2 \Delta X_{t-2} + \dots + \beta_p \Delta X_{t-p} + \lambda ECM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \tag{5}$$

Where ECM_t represents the residual, which equal to

$$Y_{t-1} - \theta X_{t-1} - cons$$

The arising problem is that how many lags we need in the ECM. When fitting models, it is possible to increase the likelihood by adding parameters, but doing so may result in over fitting. A way around this problem is to estimate p by minimizing an "information criterion." One such information criterion is the Bayes information criterion (BIC), also called Schwarz information criterion (SIC). The table implies that

ECM in different lags:

TABLE IV.

Lag	BIC	cons	d.X	l.EMC	l.d.Y	l.d.X	l2.d.Y	l2.d.X
0	9.863307	0.585	0.588***	-0.023***				
1	9.871698	0.638	0.585***	-0.023***	-0.001	-0.30		
2	9.881107	0.576	0.585***	-0.023***	0.001	-0.03	0.008	0.022

* Significant at 10% level
 ** Significant at 5% level
 *** Significant at 1% level

According to the table (4), the value of BIC for different lags in ECM can be compared. We find the ECM with zero lag has minimum value. Also, the added coefficient in the first lag and second lag in ECM is not significant at 10% level. Hence the ECM should only have first lag:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta_1 \Delta X_t + \lambda ECM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \tag{6}$$

From the equation (6), the ΔY_t is affected by three main factors: ΔX_t , the residual in previous period ECM_{t-1} and the white noise ε_t .

Ordinary Least Square is a quick method to estimate the unknown parameters in equation (6).

TABLE V.

$$\Delta Y_t = 0.585 + 0.588 \Delta X_t - 0.23 ECM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \tag{7}$$

From the table (5), we can see the t-statistics for ΔX_t and ECM_{t-1} is significant in 1% level. Focused on coefficient-0.588, series Y (soybean meal) is markedly influenced with series X (soybean) in the short term. However, the absolute value of error correction term's parameter (-0.023) is a little small. So the residual in the previous period does not affect current future price of soybean meal notably.

E. Arbitrage Strategy: Co-integration Approach

If two series are co-integrated, then the spread ($Y_t - \theta X_t$) is stationary. If one series deviates from the equilibrium line, then the series will revert to mean (α). Based on this theory, a statistical arbitrage strategy can be conducted, called Co-integration Approach (Guo, 2010). For the two series soybean meal future price (Y) and soybean future price (X), in the long-term, the fluctuation is similar. Hence, we can set a portfolio based on equation (7).

Figure (3)

When the profit of this portfolio deviates above the equilibrium value, we can predict the profit will decrease to the equilibrium level. Hence, we can sell the portfolio firstly and then close a position when the profit approximate to the mean. It means sell the portfolio at higher price level and buy it back at a lower price level. By contrast, when the profit of this portfolio lies below the equilibrium value, we can reasonably forecast that the profit will increase to the equilibrium level. Hence, we can choose to buy the portfolio in advance and close a position when the profit reverts to the mean level. That means buy the portfolio at lower price level and sell it at a higher price level.

Based on the equation (8), the arbitrage strategy can be set: sell on 1 tone soybean meal and buy 0.616 tone soybean. Figure (3) demonstrates the different region, which was used to operate co-integration arbitrage. When the profit of portfolio climb from profit region to arrive at the lower limit of selling region or reduce from observation region to reach in the upper limit of selling region, the portfolio can be bought. If the profit gets into the stop losses region, we should buy the portfolio to close a position in order to avoid unlimited losses. If the profit returns back to the equilibrium value, we should buy back the portfolio to earn profit. By comparison, if the profit lie below the equilibrium level firstly, when the profit of portfolio decrease from profit region to arrive at the lower limit of selling region or arise from observation region to reach in the upper limit of selling region, the portfolio can be sold. If the profit gets into the stop losses region, we should sell the portfolio to close a position in order to avoid unlimited losses. If the profit returns back to the equilibrium value, we should sell the portfolio to earn profit.

Table (6) introduces the regulations to buy and sell the portfolio. Meanwhile, mean represents portfolio's equilibrium value and σ represents the standard deviation for profit or loss of the portfolio. Equation (7) indicates that the equilibrium value equals to the constant 614.77 and σ is the standard deviation of residuals-156.18.

International Standard for Co-integration Strategy:

$$a_1 = 0.5 \quad a_2 = 1.2 \quad b = 1.7$$

VI. TABLE

	Open a position region	Stop loss region	Loss	Profit
Open a position-selling	$P_{upper\ limit} = mean + a_2 \times \sigma$	$P_{stop\ loss} = mean + b \times \sigma$	$(b - a_2)\sigma$	$a_2\sigma$
	$P_{lower\ limit} = mean + a_1 \times \sigma$		$(b - a_1)\sigma$	$a_1\sigma$
Open a position-buying	$P_{upper\ limit} = mean - a_2 \times \sigma$	$P_{stop\ loss} = mean - b \times \sigma$	$(b - a_2)\sigma$	$a_2\sigma$
	$P_{lower\ limit} = mean - a_1 \times \sigma$		$(b - a_1)\sigma$	$a_1\sigma$

IV. EMPIRICAL TEST

Tables 1 and 2 report the results of the stationarity and co-integration tests. The Augmented Dickey Fuller (Dickey and Fuller (1979) and Phillips-Perron test statistics (Phillips and Perron (1986)) reject the null hypotheses that the first difference in the natural logarithm of the Crush constituents futures price series are stationary, but cannot reject the null for the level series. Thus, as with most other commodity price series, there is evidence of one unit root in these futures prices. Further, the test statistics reject the null that the spreads (the difference in log of prices) are non-stationary, providing evidence that the two series are co-integrated.

The Johansen trace and maximum-eigenvalue statistics (Johansen and Juselius (1990)) presented in Table 3 provide a direct test for co-integration of the Crush constituent's futures prices. The null hypotheses of zero co-integrating vectors between the two pairs of prices ($r=0$) are rejected in both cases

at the one percent level. We can conclude that there is at least one co-integrating vector between the pairs of futures.

I. Table Unit Root Test Statistics Without Trend

Contract	$\ln(p)*100$		$\Delta \ln(p)*100$	
	ADF	PP	ADF	PP
SB	-2.32	-2.23	-36.69***	-81.12***
SM	-2.01	-1.97	-37.37***	-81.83***
SO	-1.64	-1.61	-36.80***	-81.54***
Spread 1	-4.14***	-4.81***		
Spread 2	-4.40***	-4.51***		

With Trend

ADF	$\ln(p)*100$		$\Delta \ln(p)*100$	
	PP	ADF	PP	
-2.17	-2.05	-36.70***	-81.20***	
-1.87	-1.83	-37.39***	-81.84***	
-1.48	-1.45	-36.82***	-81.55***	
-4.48***	-5.23***			
-4.40***	-4.51***			

Long-Term Equilibrium: Johansen-Juselius Maximum Likelihood Procedure Based on Maximal Eigenvalue and Trace of the Stochastic Matrix.

H ₀	H _a	λ_{max}	H ₀	H _a	λ_{trace}
Panel A: SB and SM					
r=0	r=1	26.37 ^{a***} 29.08 ^{b***} 28.56 ^{c***}	r=0	r ≥ 1	36.55 ^{a***} 40.48 ^{b***} 39.20 ^{c***}
r ≤ 1	r=2	10.17 ^{a**} 11.39 ^b 10.64 ^{c***}	r ≤ 1	r ≥ 2	10.17 ^{a**} 11.39 ^b 10.64 ^{c***}
Panel B: SB and SO					
r=0	r=1	25.01 ^{a***} 24.83 ^{b***} 24.23 ^{c***}	r=0	r ≥ 1	36.64 ^{a***} 36.88 ^{b***} 35.33 ^{c***}
r ≤ 1	r=2	11.63 ^{a**} 12.04 ^b 11.10 ^{c***}	r ≤ 1	r ≥ 2	11.63 ^{a**} 12.04 ^b 11.10 ^{c***}

Given prior evidence that the Johansen tests are sensitive to the inclusion of drift terms in its near-VAR specification (for instance, Diebold, Gardeazabal, and Yilmaz (1994)), it is worth

noting that the Johansen tests provided similar results across models with and without controls for trend.

Table 2 presents the results from equations (1) and (2) estimated outside of the GARCH system. The lag length of seven is based on the Akaike information criterion. As there is strong evidence of a long run relationship between the spread-constituents series, an error correction term is appended to the VAR system. The specification produces independently distributed residuals as indicated by the Q(24) statistics. These results are later compared to those from the joint estimation of the mean and variance equations.

The χ^2 squared statistics for the Wald test (W) reported in Table 3 suggest a strong bi-directional causality in futures prices. The significant negative coefficient of the lagged spread in the soybean price equation, coupled with the insignificant coefficient in the soy meal equation, suggests that the soybean contract bears the majority of the burden of convergence between the two prices. This is not true of soy oil. For example the significant positive coefficient of the lagged spread in the soy oil price equation, coupled with the insignificant coefficient in the soybean equation, suggests that the price convergence between soybeans and soy oil contracts do not occur and the price spread is bound to widen. This divergence in the behavior of the soy meal and soy oil in relation to soybean prices is worth a closer examination and may shed some light on the market structure for these products.

II. Table VAR Model With Error Correction - Dependent Variable: $100 * \ln(p)$

	Panel A		Panel B	
	SB	SM	SB	SO
Intercept	0.001*** (2.859)	1.95E-05 (0.059)	0.0001 (0.488)	0.004*** (4.302)
	SB		SB	
(t-1)	0.008 (0.597)	0.084 (5.852)	0.065 (4.778)	-0.007 (-0.576)
(t-2)	-0.003 (-0.242)	5.54E-05 (0.003)	-0.038*** (-2.848)	0.084*** (6.719)
(t-3)	-0.022 (-1.473)	0.056*** (3.879)	-0.005 (-0.407)	0.033*** (2.631)
(t-4)	-0.006 (-0.453)	0.021 (1.498)	0.019 (1.386)	-0.006 (-0.530)
(t-5)	-0.016 (1.089)	-0.007 (-0.495)	0.014 (1.044)	-0.004 (-0.358)
(t-6)	-0.044*** (-2.898)	0.010 (0.732)	-0.047*** (-3.472)	0.021* (1.678)
(t-7)	-0.045 (-0.045)	0.025* (1.760)	-0.035*** (-2.620)	0.019 (1.546)

	Panel A		Panel B	
	SM		SO	
(t-1)	0.208*** (13.363)	-0.074*** (-4.951)	-0.006 (0.014)	0.064*** (4.716)
(t-2)	-0.054*** (3.446)	-0.099*** (-6.555)	-0.000 (-0.033)	-0.009 (-0.682)
(t-3)	-0.073*** (4.605)	-0.038*** (-2.509)	0.039*** (2.632)	0.010 (0.796)
(t-4)	0.066*** (4.152)	-0.035*** (-2.322)	0.005 (0.399)	0.013 (0.951)
(t-5)	0.062*** (3.912)	-0.035*** (-2.344)	0.031*** (2.093)	-0.007 (-0.541)
(t-6)	0.025 (1.598)	-0.029*** (-1.942)	0.007 (0.502)	-0.017 (-1.284)
(t-7)	-0.015 (-0.015)	0.023 (1.606)	-0.036*** (-2.444)	0.012 (0.932)

	Panel A	Panel B
Spread(t-1)	-0.005*** (3.353)	0.000 (0.130)
Ha: Soy Bean → Soy Meal	W=217.07***	0.000 (0.441)
Ha: Soy Mean → Soy Bean	W=50.68***	0.005*** (4.290)
Ha: Soy Bean → Soy Oil	W=18.05***	
Ha: Soy Oil → Soy Bean	W=61.86***	
Q(24)	11.15	18.10
AIC		-5.37
Log Likelihood	20134.72	19818.53

Notes : VAR dimension is determined by minimizing the Akaike Information Criterion. ***, **, * represent significant at 1, 5, and 10 percent levels, respectively. The W statistics is for the Wald χ^2 -squared test, reported for the Granger causality tests.

V. CONCLUSION

We investigate the price discovery process between soybean futures and the, soy meal in the China. The pricing relationship between these commodities may have implications for trading strategies, imply market inefficiencies, or address the derived demand theory. Furthermore, we may find evidence regarding market microstructure theories, which maintain that the price information disseminates from more liquid markets.

In the China soybean and soymeal futures contracts are traded on the Dalian Commodity Exchange. Price fluctuations in these products affect consumers and livestock feed producers, among others. Thus, price volatility of soybean

constituents has significant income effect beyond the market for soybeans and meal products.

Our test results suggest a strong bi-directional causality in futures prices. We also find that the soybean contract bears the burden of convergence between soybean and soymeal prices. However, the same is not true in reference to soy oil prices. Thus, soy meal contracts may be more liquidity than soybeans and soy oil. The statistical findings show evidence of considerable volatility persistence for all contracts. Also, there is strong evidence of volatility spillover among these markets.

While the pronounced volatility could be due to the amount of information reaching the market, persistence in volatility may also be a reflection of the time it takes market participants to fully process the information. The evidence of volatility persistence in this study is consistent with those of other commodities and financial instruments.

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